

Cutting Tool Path Modification to Uniform Scallop-Height in Three-Axis Milling Operations

Mohsen Soori (✉ mohsen.soori@gmail.com)

University of Kyrenia: Girne Universitesi <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4358-7513>

Behrooz Arezoo

Amirkabir University of Technology

Research Article

Keywords: Scallop-Height, Cutting tool path Modification, Surface quality, Three-Axis milling, Virtual machining

Posted Date: November 14th, 2022

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2137112/v1>

License: This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. [Read Full License](#)

Abstract

Scallop height, which is the uncut amount of workpiece materials in metal cutting paths, has an impact on the surface condition of manufactured products. To increase accuracy and surface quality of machined parts, the scallop height should be analyzed in order to be minimized. In this study, a virtual machining system is created to produce uniform scallop height throughout free form surface end milling. Machined surfaces are analyzed by the developed system in order to obtain the curvature of free form surfaces. Then, the machined surfaces are divided to the flat, concave and convex surfaces in order to analyze and modify the cutting tool paths along milling operations. The machining parameters of step over, feed rate and spindle speed are modified in order to obtain uniform scallop height during milling operations of free form surfaces. As a result, the modified cutting tool paths can generate the uniform scallop height in order to increase surface quality of machined free form surfaces. To enhance the process of component manufacturing utilizing machining operations, the study's produced virtual machining system can raise the productivity as well as the accuracy of machined free from surfaces.

1 Introduction

The cutting tool paths of free from surfaces are normally involving a huge number of tool movements. Scallop height of machined surfaces is the uncut area left across two adjacent cutting tool tracks during the chip production process. It is defined as the local maximum of the uncut volume thickness from the workpiece material surfaces in chip formation process. It is critical to examine and control the scallop height throughout milling operations of free form surfaces in terms of improving the surface properties of manufactured parts. So, in order to increase accuracy and quality of part production, the cutting tool paths can be modified to provide the uniform scallop height during milling operations.

To create constant scallop height during milling operations of complex curved surface parts, modified cutting tool paths is generated by Jia et al. [1]. In order to calculate the scallop height in milling operation with torus-end cutter, an analytical model by considering the feed rate effects is developed by Segonds et al. [2]. To predict the scallop height in the cutting of surface layer, advanced software system by using numerical curve fitting techniques is developed by Kukreja and Pande [3]. To provide constant scallop height during plunge milling operations of pocket walls, advanced tool paths modification system with adaptive interval method is investigated by Huang et al. [4]. Shchurov and Al-Taie provide an innovative project of cutting tool path adjustment in order to maintain a consistent scallop height throughout free form surface end milling [5]. To increase surface quality during 5-axis milling operations of free form surfaces, modified cutting tool paths modification regarding the uniform scallop height of machined surfaces is presented by Lin et al. [6]. In order to provide uniform scallop height in milling operations of free form surfaces, modified cutting tool paths is presented by Senatore et al. [7]. Advanced cutting tool path planning system is developed by Liang et al. [8] in order to provide the universal iso-scallop during milling operations of free form surfaces. To provide iso-scallop during 3-axis CNC machining of free-form rectangular meshed textures, the tool path modification system based on cutting tool performance metric is developed by Balabokhin and Tarbuton [9]. Advanced method of efficient iso-scallop cutting tool path is presented by Liu et al. [10] to increase surface quality of machined parts during three-axis scattered cloud machining operations. To increase surface quality by providing uniform scallop during machining operations of sculptured surfaces, optimized cutting tool paths is presented by Fountas et al. [11]. To achieve the uniform scallop height and increase surface quality of during machining operations of free form

surfaces, advanced barrel cutting tool design and cutting tool path planning system is presented by Luo et al. [12].

To improve surface properties in terms of cutting of big polygons using 5-axis mill with flat milling cutter, the scallop height of machined surfaces are analyzed by Duvedi et al. [13]. To provide the constant scallop height during grinding operations of convex surfaces, advanced tool path generation algorithm is presented by Wang et al. [14]. To achieve the iso-scallop height during milling operations of free form surfaces, optimized cutting tool paths is presented by Cao et al. [15]. In order to increase surface quality in spiral machining operations of free-form surfaces, physical shell mapping and reverse-compensation optimization is presented by Li et al. [16]. Optimization of cutting tool by using digital images is presented by Xu and Li [17] in order to provide uniform scallop height during milling operations of free form surfaces. Advanced cutting tool paths modification is presented by Su et al. [18] to get a consistent scallop level while cutting free form edges.

Soori et al. provide virtual machining methodologies to assess and improve cnc machining in virtual worlds [19–22]. Soori et al. provides a review of current developments in friction stir welding techniques in order to examine and improve efficiency in the process of component manufacturing employing welding procedures [23]. Soori and Asamel have explored implementations of virtual machining systems to reduce residual stress and deflection error throughout turbine blade five-axis milling processes [24]. Soori and Asmael created implementations of virtualized machining system in evaluating and decreasing the cutting temperature throughout milling operations of hard to cut components [25].

Soori et al. proposed an improved virtual machining method to improve surface properties throughout five-axis milling operations of turbine blades [26]. Soori and Asmael devised virtual milling techniques to reduce deflection error during five-axis milling processes of impeller blades [27]. Soori and Asmael provided a summary of existing developments from published articles in order to examine and improve the parameter optimization technique of machining processes [28]. Dastres et al. give a study of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) based wireless manufacturing systems to improve energy utilization efficiency, data quality and availability across the supply chain, and precision and dependability during the component production process[29].

Altintas and Merdol also proposed a virtual machining system and application in order to achieve optimum milling settings [30]. According to the analysis of previous published papers, the area of Uniform Scallop-Height in Three-Axis Milling Operations of free form surfaces is not investigated by employing virtual machining systems.

In the research work, application of the virtual machining system is investigated in order to create the uniform scallop height during milling operations of free from surfaces using three-axis CNC milling machine tools. The surfaces of workpiece are analyzed in order to obtain the curvature of machined surfaces. As a result, the free form surfaces are divided to the flat, concave and convex surfaces to examine and improve cutting tool paths along milling operations. Modified machining parameters as step over, feed rate and spindle speed are generated by using the developed system in the study in order to provide a uniform scallop height during milling operations.

In order to validate the study, a sample workpiece with free form surfaces is produced by employing the three-axis CNC machine tools. Then, the machined surfaces are measured by ZeGage Optical surface profiler to calculate the scallop height of cutting tool paths in the end milling processes.

The mathematical equations of the scallop heights during milling operations of flat, concave and convex surfaces are presented in section 2. The Section 3 of the research presents the created virtual machining system. To validate the research work, the section 4 is presented. Eventually, in section 5, the research findings are discussed.

2 Scallop-height In Machined Surfaces

In the milling operations, there are two kinds of scallop height which create the pattern of machined surfaces. The scallop height in X-axis direction is tool-nose cut scallop height which is generated as a result of feed rate of cutting tool along machining path (f). The scallop height in Y-axis direction is tool-edge cut scallop height due to cutting tool nose radius and step over (p) during milling operation [31]. The scallop height of machined surfaces in X and Y-axis directions is shown in the Fig. 1.

The duration of feed rate per rotation (mm/rev) can be presented as,

$$f = \frac{F_c}{S}$$

1

Where, F_c is feed rate of cutting (mm/min) and S is speed of spindle (rev/min).

To calculate the scallop height in the Y-axis direction, the milling paths can be divided by flat, concave and convex surfaces. As a result, they can be modelled by using mathematical equations. The scallop height during milling operations of flat surfaces, is shown in the Fig. 2.

According to the geometric relations in the Fig. 2, the scallop height in the flat surfaces can be obtained as,

$$R^2 = \left(\frac{p}{2}\right)^2 + (R - H)^2$$

2

As a result,

$$p = 4\sqrt{R^2 - (R - H)^2}$$

3

Where R is nose radius of the cutter, H is the scallop height and p is the cutting tool path interval.

The scallop height during milling operations of concave surfaces is shown in the Fig. 3.

So, the path interval during milling operations of convex surfaces can be obtained as,

$$p = \frac{Rw}{(Rw + H)(Rw + Rt)} \sqrt{2 \left[(Rw + Rt)^2 + Rt^2 \right] (Rw + H)^2 - [(Rw + Rt)^2 - Rt^2]^2 - (Rw + H)^4}$$

4

where R_w is curvature radius of workpiece, R_t is the cutting tool radius, P is the cutting tool path interval, and H is the scallop height. In the Fig. 4, the scallop height during milling operations of concave surface is shown.

So, the path interval of the cutting tool during milling operation can be obtained as,

$$p = \frac{R_w}{(R_w - H)(R_w + R_t)} \sqrt{2 \left[(R_w + R_t)^2 + R_t^2 \right] (R_w - H)^2 - \left[(R_w + R_t)^2 - R_t^2 \right]^2 - (R_w - H)^4}$$

4

3 Virtual Machining System To Uniform Scallop-height

The study develops a virtual machining system using the Matlab programming language to ensure constant scallop height throughout milling processes of free form plates. The limitation of scallop height, NC codes, cutting circumstances and cutter shape, as well as a CAD representation of the workpiece are input to the system. The curvature of machined surfaces is determined by analyzing the surfaces of the workpiece. So, the free form surfaces have been split up into convex, concave and flat surfaces to provide the uniform scallop height of H during the chip creation process. Then, the system can calculate the amount of step over, step over, feed rate and spindle speed along the cutting tool paths. Then, modified machining parameters regarding the limitation of scallop height during machining operations of free form surfaces can be obtained. Thus, by using the modified cutting tool paths, the desired uniform of the scallop height H during milling operations of free form surfaces can be obtained. The flowchart of the virtual machining system to generate the uniform scallop height is presented in the Fig. 5.

4 Validation

To verify the research work, sample workpiece with the presented dimensions in the Fig. 6 is considered to be milled and measured.

The milling cutter pathways are generated using Mastercam's CAM program, as illustrated in Fig. 7.

The 5-axis Kondia HM 1060 CNC machine tool is utilized in experimental workpiece milling processes. The used cutting tool is 4 fluted Tungsten carbide ball nose end-mill with 15 mm diameter and overall length 70 mm and flute length 35 mm. The speed of spindle is 10000 rpm, step over 4 mm and feed rate 280 mm/min. Figure 8 depicts the milling procedures on the sample workpiece.

As a result, the machined sample workpiece is shown in the Fig. 9.

The virtual machining system is used in order to provide the desired scallop height $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. So, the speed of spindle is 12000 rpm, step over 0.5 mm and feed rate 210 mm/min. To measure the scallop height of cutting tool paths during milling operations, the machined surfaces of sample workpiece are measured by ZeGage Optical surface profiler. In the optical surface quality measurement process, the light is separated into two routes, one of which travels to a precise reference surface and the other to the test surface, in order to assess the condition of the surface of the sample part. The reflections from these two surfaces collide at a camera detector, resulting in a pattern of light and dark intensities. As a consequence, the constructive interference reveals the surface

characteristics of the sample workpiece. The principle of 3D optical surface measuring system to obtain the surface quality of sample workpiece is shown in the Fig. 11.

The measurement process of scallop height of cutting tool paths by using the ZeGage Optical surface profiler is shown in the Fig. 10.

As a result, the measured scallop height of machined sample workpiece for the sample line AB by using the ZeGage Optical surface profiler is obtained as the Fig. 12.

So, the measured data for the sample line AB in the obtained 3D data of machined sample workpiece can be presented in the Fig. 13.

Also, the measured scallop height of machined sample workpiece for the sample line CD is presented as Fig. 14.

Moreover, the measured data for the sample line CD in the obtained 3D data of machined sample workpiece surface can be presented in the Fig. 15.

By using the modified cutting tool paths in the study, the maximum scallop height of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ is obtained in the machined and measured sample workpiece. As a result, utilizing the 3-axis CNC milling machine tools, the improved cutting tool paths created by the proposed virtual machining system in the study can offer consistent scallop height in the machining operations of free from interfaces.

5 Conclusion

Scallop height of machined surfaces is uncut volume tracks between two neighboring of machined surface during the chip production process. In the chip creation process, it is defined as the local maximum of the uncut volume thickness from the workpiece material surfaces. As a conclusion, the scallop height should be evaluated and controlled in order to improve the surface properties of machined components. The application of the virtual machining system is introduced in the research work to achieve consistent scallop height throughout end milling of free form areas. The developed virtual machining system analyzes machined surfaces in order to determine the curvature of free form surfaces. The machined surfaces are then split into flat, concave, and convex surfaces so that the cutting tool trajectories can be analyzed and modified during milling operations. So, new machining parameters of step over, feed rate and spindle speed are created by applying the developed system to provide desired scallop height in the free form surface of machined part. A sample workpiece with free form surfaces is machined and surfaces of machined parts are optically measured in order to obtain the 3D model of scallop height. As a result, the maximum scallop height of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ is obtained in the machined and measured sample workpiece in the validation section of the study. The virtual machining technology can be extended to 5-axis CNC milling operations to improve the surface properties of machined products with free form surfaces like turbine blades and impellers. These are the authors' ideas for future research projects.

Declarations

Availability of data and materials

The used data and materials in the research works are available.

Competing interests

There is no conflict of interest regarding the submitted manuscript

Funding

There is no funding for the submitted manuscript.

Authors' contributions

All authors are contributed in the research works as idea development, data collection/analysis, paper writing and submission. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

References

1. Jia, Z.-y., et al., *Toolpath generation in sub-regional processing with constraint of constant scallop-height at boundary for complex curved surface*. Precision Engineering, 2019. **55**: p. 217-230.
2. Segonds, S., et al., *An analytical model taking feed rate effect into consideration for scallop height calculation in milling with torus-end cutter*. Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing, 2019. **30**(4): p. 1881-1893.
3. Kukreja, A. and S. Pande, *Estimation of scallop height in freeform surface CNC Machining*. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 2019. **104**(9): p. 4231-4242.
4. Huang, N., et al., *Plunge milling with constant scallop height by adaptively modifying the step interval for pocket wall*. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 2019. **101**(1): p. 203-208.
5. Shchurov, I. and L. Al-Taie, *Constant scallop-height tool path generation for ball-end mill cutters and three-axis cnc milling machines*. Procedia Engineering, 2017. **206**: p. 1137-1141.
6. Lin, Z., et al., *A generic uniform scallop tool path generation method for five-axis machining of freeform surface*. Computer-Aided Design, 2014. **56**: p. 120-132.
7. Senatore, J., et al., *Analysis of drift in iso-scallop planning—machining by regions*. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 2013. **67**(1-4): p. 719-732.
8. Liang, F., et al., *Iso-scallop tool path planning for triangular mesh surfaces in multi-axis machining*. Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing, 2021. **72**: p. 102206.
9. Balabokhin, A. and J. Tarbutton, *Iso-scallop tool path building algorithm “based on tool performance metric” for generalized cutter and arbitrary milling zones in 3-axis CNC milling of free-form triangular meshed surfaces*. Journal of Manufacturing Processes, 2017. **28**: p. 565-572.
10. Liu, W., et al., *An efficient iso-scallop tool path generation method for three-axis scattered point cloud machining*. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 2020. **107**(7): p. 3471-3483.
11. Fountas, N.A., et al., *Globally optimal tool paths for sculptured surfaces with emphasis to machining error and cutting posture smoothness*. International Journal of Production Research, 2019. **57**(17): p. 5478-5498.

12. Luo, M., et al., *Barrel cutter design and toolpath planning for high-efficiency machining of freeform surface*. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 2016. **85**(9): p. 2495-2503.
13. Duvedi, R.K., et al., *Scallop height of 5-axis machining of large triangles with a flat end mill*. Computer-Aided Design and Applications, 2015. **12**(6): p. 710-716.
14. Wang, S.-l., et al., *A novel tool path generation algorithm for plane envelope grinding convex surface based on constant scallop height method*. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 2015. **78**(5-8): p. 1087-1099.
15. Cao, S.K., et al. *Free surface NC machining tool path optimization algorithm based on the iso-scallop method*. in *Applied Mechanics and Materials*. 2015. Trans Tech Publ.
16. Li, X., et al., *Combining physical shell mapping and reverse-compensation optimisation for spiral machining of free-form surfaces*. International Journal of Production Research, 2019. **57**(13): p. 4118-4131.
17. Xu, K. and Y. Li, *Digital image approach to tool path generation for surface machining*. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 2019. **101**(9): p. 2547-2558.
18. Su, C., et al., *Initial tool path selection of the iso-scallop method based on offset similarity analysis for global preferred feed directions matching*. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 2020. **106**(7): p. 2675-2687.
19. Soori, M., B. Arezoo, and M. Habibi, *Accuracy analysis of tool deflection error modelling in prediction of milled surfaces by a virtual machining system*. International Journal of Computer Applications in Technology, 2017. **55**(4): p. 308-321.
20. Soori, M., B. Arezoo, and M. Habibi, *Virtual machining considering dimensional, geometrical and tool deflection errors in three-axis CNC milling machines*. Journal of Manufacturing Systems, 2014. **33**(4): p. 498-507.
21. Soori, M., B. Arezoo, and M. Habibi, *Dimensional and geometrical errors of three-axis CNC milling machines in a virtual machining system*. Computer-Aided Design, 2013. **45**(11): p. 1306-1313.
22. Soori, M., B. Arezoo, and M. Habibi, *Tool deflection error of three-axis computer numerical control milling machines, monitoring and minimizing by a virtual machining system*. Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering, 2016. **138**(8).
23. Soori, M., M. Asmael, and D. Solyali, *Recent Development in Friction Stir Welding Process: A Review*. SAE International Journal of Materials and Manufacturing, 2020(5): p. 18.
24. Soori, M. and M. Asmael, *Virtual Minimization of Residual Stress and Deflection Error in Five-Axis Milling of Turbine Blades*. Strojnicki Vestnik/ Journal of Mechanical Engineering, 2021. **67**(5): p. 235-244.
25. Soori, M. and M. Asmael, *Cutting temperatures in milling operations of difficult-to-cut materials*. Journal of New Technology and Materials, 2021. **11**(1): p. 47-56.
26. Soori, M., et al., *Minimization of surface roughness in 5-axis milling of turbine blades*. Mechanics Based Design of Structures and Machines, 2021: p. 1-18.
27. Soori, M. and M. Asmael, *MINIMIZATION OF DEFLECTION ERROR IN FIVE AXIS MILLING OF IMPELLER BLADES*. Facta Universitatis, series: Mechanical Engineering, 2021.
28. Soori, M. and M. Asmael, *A Review of the Recent Development in Machining Parameter Optimization*. Jordan Journal of Mechanical & Industrial Engineering, 2022. **16**(2): p. 205-223.

29. Dastres, R., M. Soori, and M. Asmael, *RADIO FREQUENCY IDENTIFICATION (RFID) BASED WIRELESS MANUFACTURING SYSTEMS, A REVIEW*. Independent Journal of Management & Production, 2022. **13**(1): p. 258-290.
30. Altintas, Y. and S. Merdol, *Virtual high performance milling*. CIRP annals, 2007. **56**(1): p. 81-84.
31. Wang, S., S. To, and C.F. Cheung, *An investigation into material-induced surface roughness in ultra-precision milling*. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology, 2013. **68**(1-4): p. 607-616.

Figures

Removed materials per cutting tool rotation

Figure 1

The scallop height of areas that were milled in the X and Y axes.

Figure 2

Scallop-height in flat surface.

Figure 3

Scallop-height in convex surface

Figure 4

Scallop-height in concave surface.

Figure 5

The flowchart of the virtual machining system to generate the uniform scallop height.

Figure 6

The sample workpiece in the experiment.

Figure 7

The cutting tool paths.

Figure 8

Machining operations of sample workpiece.

Figure 9

Machined sample workpiece.

Figure 10

The measurement process of scallop height of cutting tool paths by using the ZeGage Optical surface profiler.

Figure 11

The principle of 3D optical surface measuring system to obtain the surface quality of sample workpiece.

Figure 12

The measured scallop height of machined surface of sample workpiece.

Figure 13

The measured data for the sample line AB in the obtained 3D data of machined sample workpiece surface in the figure 12.

Figure 14

The measured scallop height of machined surface of sample workpiece.

Figure 15

The measured data for the sample line CD in the obtained 3D data of machined sample workpiece surface in the figure 14.